

Modeling Uganda's Path to Universal Electrification by 2040: A Least-Cost Approach Using OnSSET

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ABBREVIATIONS

AFDB – African Development Bank
ERA – Electricity Regulatory Authority
ESMAP – Energy Sector Management Assistance Program
ESWG – Energy Sector Working Group
GEP – Global Electrification Platform
GIS – Geographic Information System
IEA – International Energy Agency
IPPs – Independent Power Producers
IRENA – International Renewable Energy Agency
MEMD – Ministry of Energy and Mineral Development
MV – Medium Voltage
HV – High Voltage
OnSSET – Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool
PV – Photovoltaic
QGIS – Quantum Geographic Information System
REA – Rural Electrification Agency
SHS – Solar Home Systems
UBOS – Uganda Bureau of Statistics
UEDCL – Uganda Electricity Distribution Company Limited
UEGCL – Uganda Electricity Generation Company Limited
UETCL – Uganda Electricity Transmission Company Limited

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Uganda's electrification ambitions, as outlined in Vision 2040 and the Energy Policy 2023, call for universal electricity access by 2040. This report presents a spatially grounded analysis developed using the Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) during the EMP-G 2025 training. The analysis evaluates two distinct electrification scenarios, each designed to meet national targets of 80% by 2030 and universal electrification by 2040 while considering demographic trends, infrastructure limitations, and fiscal realities. The first scenario, referred to as the Forced Grid Approach, assumes a centralized strategy where the national grid is extended to all settlements, regardless of cost-effectiveness. In contrast, the Nationwide Least-Cost Approach applies a decentralized, data-driven methodology that selects the most economically viable technology—grid, mini-grid, or standalone—for each location. Both scenarios incorporate 2040 projections, including a population of 65.8 million, 60% urbanization, and average household sizes of 4 persons per household in rural areas and 3.4 persons per household in urban areas. While both scenarios achieve universal access, the Least-Cost Approach does so with USD 1.8 billion less investment. It also delivers a higher share of off-grid connections, particularly in rural and hard-to-reach areas, where grid extension would be prohibitively expensive. This approach reduces the burden on public infrastructure and aligns with Uganda's current financing landscape. It leverages private sector participation and donor-backed initiatives such as the Beyond the Grid Fund for Africa, which supports the development of mini-grids in underserved regions. The model also supports smarter grid investments, lower emissions, and greater flexibility in planning. The report recommends that Uganda adopt the Nationwide Least-Cost Approach as the foundation for its electrification strategy. This pathway not only meets national access targets but also ensures a more equitable, cost-effective, and resilient energy future.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Uganda's current electrification landscape

Uganda's electricity sector is undergoing a major transformation, guided by national frameworks such as Vision 2040, the National Development Plan IV (NDP IV), and the Energy Policy for Uganda (2023). These policies collectively target universal electricity access by 2040 as a driver of socio-economic development and industrialization.

As of 2024, Uganda's electricity access rate stands at approximately 57%, with only 19% of households connected to the national grid. The remainder rely on off-grid solutions such as solar home systems, diesel generators, and other decentralized technologies. Despite an installed generation capacity exceeding 1,300 MW, electricity consumption remains low due to limited last-mile connectivity, affordability barriers, and underutilized demand.

1.2 Key Institutions involved

The sector is anchored by several key institutions. The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Development (MEMD) leads policy formulation and planning. The Electricity Regulatory Authority (ERA) oversees licensing and tariff regulation. Uganda Electricity Transmission Company Limited (UETCL), Uganda Electricity Distribution Company Limited (UEDCL), and Uganda Electricity Generation Company Limited (UEGCL) manage infrastructure across the value chain. In addition, private actors such as WENRECO, Independent Power Producers (IPPs), mini-grid developers, and solar companies play a growing role in expanding access.

1.3 Key challenges

Uganda's electrification efforts face persistent challenges. Although the average distance from settlements to medium-voltage grid lines is approximately 3.7 km—a relatively short distance by regional standards—many communities remain unconnected due to high connection costs, limited utility financing, and the scattered nature of rural settlements. Despite a generation capacity exceeding 1,300 MW, only about half of the available electricity is consumed. This underutilization is primarily due to limited last-mile connectivity and low household demand. Of the electricity that is consumed, approximately 22% is used by households, while the remaining 78% serves commercial and industrial users. This imbalance contributes to elevated tariffs and financial strain on the sector.

1.4 Purpose and Scope

This report assesses Uganda's electrification strategy by modeling alternative pathways to achieve 100% electricity access by 2040. Using the Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET), the study applies spatial least-cost modeling to evaluate technology options, investment needs, and access outcomes under different scenarios. The analysis was

developed as part of the EMP-G 2025 training and aims to inform national planning and policy decisions.

1.5 Objective and Aims

The primary objective is to identify the most cost-effective and inclusive strategy for achieving universal access. Specifically, the study aims to:

- Simulate and compare electrification scenarios targeting 80% access by 2030 and 100% by 2040.
- Evaluate least-cost technology mixes, including grid, mini-grid, and standalone systems.
- Generate spatially referenced outputs to support planning and investment decisions.

1.6 Alignment to Mission 300 and Vision 2040

This work supports broader regional initiatives such as Mission 300, led by the African Development Bank and the World Bank, which aims to connect 300 million people in Africa by 2030. It also aligns with Uganda's Vision 2040 and NDP IV, which prioritize energy access as a foundation for inclusive growth, industrialization, and improved quality of life.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Modeling Framework and Planning Approach

This study applies a bottom-up, geospatial least-cost planning methodology using the Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET). OnSSET is a Python-based modeling platform designed to identify the most cost-effective electrification technology—grid, mini-grid, or standalone—for each unserved settlement. It supports scenario-based planning by simulating access expansion under different policy, demographic, and financial constraints.

The modeling process involved the integration of spatial datasets, calibration of demand assumptions, and sensitivity testing of key parameters such as PV costs and grid connection thresholds. The outputs provide a spatially disaggregated view of electrification options, supporting evidence-based planning and investment prioritization.

At the core of OnSSET is an electrification algorithm that selects the technology configuration with the lowest Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) for each location.

The LCOE represents the average cost per kilowatt-hour required for a system to break even over its operational lifetime, incorporating capital, operational, and maintenance costs.

$$LCOE = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{I_t + O\&M_t + F_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}}$$

Where:

- I_t : Investment expenditure for a specific system in year t ,
- $O\&M_t$: the operation and maintenance costs,
- F_t : the fuel expenditures,
- E_t : the generated electricity,
- r : the discount rate,
- n : the lifetime of the system.

This metric enables a consistent comparison across technologies and geographies, ensuring that the selected solution is both technically feasible and economically optimal.

2.2 Data Sources

The GIS datasets were sourced from different sites as shown in table 1 below.

Table 1: Datasets used and sources

Dataset	Purpose	Source
Population raster	Spatial distribution of population at high resolution	World Population

Wind Velocity	For hybrid mini-grid modeling	Global Wind Atlas
Global Horizontal Irradiance	Determines PV system performance	Global Solar Atlas
Hydro Potential	For mini-grid hydro modeling	ESWG, Energy data Info
Landcover	Used to estimate construction difficulty and costs	Copernicus
Existing MV lines	Determines proximity to grid and cost of extension	ESWG
Existing HV lines	Helps define grid backbone and transmission capacity	ESWG
Road Network	Used to estimate accessibility and infrastructure costs	OpenStreetMap
Elevation	Affects grid extension costs and solar potential	SRTM
Healthcare and education facilities	Prioritization of social infrastructure	HumData.org
Administrative boundaries	Defines national, district, and sub-county boundaries for spatial aggregation	GADM, UBOS
Existing Mini-Grids	Identifies already electrified off-grid areas	ESWG
Travel time	Estimates accessibility to cities and logistics costs	Malaria Atlas Project
Night lights	Detect where electricity is likely already used or needed	Earth observation group
Custom Demand	Define how much electricity is needed and by whom	KTH

The non-GIS datasets which included national demographics and technology costs were obtained from UBOS 2024, National Electrification Strategy, UMEME, UETCL, UEDCL, ERA, Equator Power among others.

2.3 Scenarios Modeled

To explore different electrification pathways, two main scenarios were modeled: Least cost – High Demand and Forced Grid – High Demand with assumptions as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 2: Scenario assumptions from demand and supply side.

	Forced Grid Approach	Least Cost Approach
Demand side assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Normal population growth of 2.9% ● Urbanization rate of 60% by 2040 ● Tier 4 for urban settlements, Tier 3 for large rural settlements and Tier 2 for small rural settlements. ● 80% electrification by 2030 ● 100% electrification by 2040 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Normal population growth of 2.9% ● Urbanization rate of 60% by 2040 ● Tier 4 for urban settlements, Tier 3 for large rural settlements and Tier 2 for small rural settlements. ● 80% electrification by 2030 ● 100% electrification by 2040
Supply side assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Grid prioritized for all settlements within 4 km of existing lines. ● 200MW grid capacity limit. ● Grid Generation Cost of 0.062 USD/kWh ● No limit on maximum number of new grid connections per year ● Baseline market PV cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technology selected based on least-cost per settlement. ● 200MW grid capacity limit. ● Grid Generation Cost of 0.062 USD/kWh ● 400,000 maximum new grid connections per year ● 20% discount for SHS and 15% for Mini-Grids ● PV cost kept at expected cost

3. RESULTS

3.1 Forced Grid Approach Scenario

The forced grid electrification scenario prioritizes grid extension and densification as the primary mode of delivering electricity access across Uganda. This approach assumes policy-driven grid expansion, even in areas where off-grid solutions might otherwise be more cost-effective.

Under this scenario, a total of 2369.95 MW of capacity (table 2) is projected to be added between 2030 and 2040, requiring a significantly higher investment of USD 10.64 billion. Despite the higher cost, the strategy achieves 11.3 million new connections, with 86.2% (56.8 million people) connected through the national grid, and only 13.7% (9 million people) relying on off-grid technologies such as Solar Home Systems (SHS) and PV mini-grids.

The number of new mini-grids added is projected to be just 9, reflecting the minimal role assigned to off-grid solutions in this scenario.

Table 3: Capacity (MW) required for electrification under forced grid approach.

TECHNOLOGY	2030 (MW)	2040 (MW)	TOTAL (MW)
Grid Densification	504.81	1634.11	2138.92
Existing Grid	42.42	54.8	97.22
Solar Home Systems	44.74	79.96	124.7
PV Mini-Grid	0.33	8.78	9.11
TOTAL			2369.95 MW

3.1.1 Analysis

In this electrification scenario, as shown in the figure below, with a grid generation cost of 0.062 USD/kWh, the grid densification emerges as the dominant pathway, accounting for 55.21% of new connections exhibiting a relatively high average power demand of 342.6 W, which reflects reflecting proximity a user base with higher-tier energy needs.

Grid extension contributes 20.26% of new connections, though with a significantly lower average demand of 42.4 W indicating it serves remote or lower-income communities where basic energy access is the priority.

Solar Home Systems (SHS) deliver 24.36% of new connections. With an average power consumption of 45.3 W, SHS are well-suited for dispersed rural households requiring essential services such as lighting and phone charging.

Mini-grids represent a small share—just 0.17% of new connections—they serve the highest average demand at 463.6 W indicating deployment in commercial areas.

Figure 1: Comparison of total investment (million USD) vs total new connections by 2040 – forced grid scenario

Figure 2: Map showing Forced Grid Scenario 2040 result visualization in QGIS

3.2 Least Cost Approach Scenario

This least-cost electrification scenario prioritizes technologies based on the lowest cost per settlement, while incorporating key constraints such as a 200 MW annual grid capacity limit, a grid generation cost of 0.062 USD/kWh, and a cap of 400,000 new grid connections per year. The model applies a 20% discount for Solar Home Systems (SHS) and 15% for mini-grids, with PV costs held at baseline levels.

Under these conditions, a total of 2421.75 MW of new capacity is projected to be added by 2040 (Table 4), requiring an investment of approximately USD 8.83 billion. Despite the higher cost, the strategy achieves 11.3 million new connections, with 75.7% (49.8 million people) connected through the national grid and an increment to 24.3 % (16 million people) served by off-grid technologies. Notably, 18 new mini-grids are projected, underscoring the limited role of off-grid systems in this scenario.

Table 4: Capacity (MW) required for electrification under least cost approach.

TECHNOLOGY	2030 (MW)	2040 (MW)	TOTAL (MW)
Grid Densification	504.81	1634.11	2138.92
Existing Grid	14.73	5.02	19.75
Solar Home Systems	93.86	148.47	242.33
PV Mini-Grid	1.22	19.53	20.75
TOTAL			2421.75 (MW)

3.2.1. Analysis

In this electrification scenario, as shown in the figure below, grid densification is the leading pathway, contributing 55.21% of new connections with an average demand of 342.6 W, reflecting dense settlements near existing infrastructure and higher-tier energy needs.

Grid extension accounts for just 1.08%, with a moderate 161.3 W per connection, suggesting limited deployment in favor of off-grid solutions.

Standalone Solar Home Systems (SHS) provide 43.32% of connections, averaging 49.5 W, consistent with basic energy access in remote areas.

Though mini-grids make up only 0.39%, they serve the highest average demand at 475.6 W, indicating targeted use in commercial or semi-industrial zones.

Figure 3: Comparison of total investment (million USD) vs total new connections by 2040 - Least cost scenario

Figure 4: Map showing Least cost scenario 2040 result visualization in QGIS

3.3 Comparison between Scenarios

The two electrification scenarios—Least Cost Approach and Forced Grid Approach—offer contrasting strategies for achieving Uganda’s universal access target by 2040. While both reach the same number of new connections (11.3 million), their investment profiles and technology mixes differ significantly.

Table 4: Comparison between the two scenarios

PARAMETERS	SCENARIO 1: LEAST COST APPROACH	SCENARIO 2: FORCED GRID APPROACH
Capacity (MW)	2421.75	2369.95
Investment (million \$)	8837.31	10647.19
New Connections	11308013	11308013
Emissions ((tCO ₂))	2287.79	2296.62
Population connected to the grid	49,833,350	56,803,458
Population connected to off-grid options	16,040,921	9,070,812

3.3.1 Key Observations

- The Least Cost Approach achieves the same access target with USD 1.8 billion less investment. It prioritizes SHS and minimizes grid extension, making it more suitable for dispersed rural populations.
- The Forced Grid Approach allocates over 86% of investment to grid infrastructure, which may not be optimal for low-demand areas.
- The Least Cost model offers greater flexibility and cost-efficiency, especially in areas where grid expansion is economically unviable.

4.0 DISCUSSION

The analysis compared annual investment requirements and financing structures under two electrification scenarios—Forced Grid Approach and Least Cost Approach—against the current baseline allocation of \$300 million (assumed to be fully allocated to grid expansion) as shown in table below.

SCENARIO	Annual Investment (million USD)	%Grid Investment	Grid Budget Requirement	Out of Budget Investment	Private Capital (SHS, Mini-Grids)
Baseline 2025	300	100	300	-	-
Least Cost	631.2	69.18	436.6	136.6	194.6
Forced Grid	760.5	86.42	657.2	357.2	103.3

Key findings include;

- The Forced Grid Approach requires the highest annual investment of \$760.5 million, which is 2.5 times the current baseline. This heavy reliance on grid expansion results in a substantial out-of-budget investment burden of \$357.2 million, and only a modest contribution from private capital (\$103.3 million). This makes it fiscally challenging and places most of the burden on public financing.
- The Least Cost Approach although still above current levels, the required investment of \$631.2 million represents a more financially viable pathway. It demands \$436.6 million in public grid investment—\$136.6 million more than current levels—but benefits from significantly higher private sector participation (\$194.6 million). This approach more efficiently blends public and private capital and reduces the overall fiscal strain.

4.1 Limitations

- The model uses generalized household demand tiers, which do not capture inter-regional differences or evolving consumption patterns across Uganda.
- Household electricity needs are assumed constant, excluding future growth or behavioral shifts.
- Future cost trends for SHS and mini-grids are estimated but may not reflect actual market dynamics.
- Environmental and climate-related vulnerabilities are not factored.
- The model assumes stable policy and funding environments.

4.2 Recommendations

- The Least Cost Approach provides a more balanced investment strategy by leveraging nearly \$200 million in private capital annually while keeping public

budget increases relatively moderate. This model should be prioritized in national planning frameworks.

- The Forced Grid Approach results in costly infrastructure that may not be the most economical for low-demand or remote areas. Extending the grid without considering local demand densities should be avoided.
- Government should strengthen policies and incentives—such as tax exemptions and risk mitigation instruments—to encourage further private investment in solar home systems and mini-grids, especially in underserved rural areas.
- National electrification strategies must reflect the true annual financing gap and move beyond the outdated baseline of \$300 million. Forward-looking budgeting should aim for at least \$436.6 million in public grid investment under the Least Cost scenario.
- Least-cost modelling outputs should guide regional and district-level planning, ensuring that public funds are allocated where they yield the greatest return in terms of access expansion.
- Consider commercial demand to prioritize electrification in areas with high potential for agriculture, agro-processing, tourism, and small-scale industries.
- Design electrification plans starting from realistic national and sub-national budget allocations.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 Conclusion

This study set out to determine the most effective and financially feasible strategy for achieving universal electricity access in Uganda by 2040. Using the OnSSET model, two scenarios were simulated and compared: the Forced Grid Approach, which emphasizes nationwide grid expansion, and the Least Cost Approach, which selects the most economical technology per settlement. The analysis concludes that the Least Cost Approach is the most effective pathway to achieving 100% access by 2040. It delivers the same number of new connections as the Forced Grid scenario but with USD 1.8 billion less investment, while offering a more balanced technology mix that reduces reliance on costly grid extensions. It also provides critical investment and policy insights by demonstrating how public and private capital can be blended to close the financing gap, making it not only technically sound but also economically and institutionally realistic. Furthermore, the scenario aligns with Uganda's Vision 2040 and Energy Policy 2023, while supporting regional initiatives like Mission 300. It promotes faster deployment, private sector participation, and smarter grid investments—positioning it as the most strategic foundation for Uganda's national electrification planning.

5.2 Future work

- Develop a scenario that optimizes the use of Uganda's current medium-voltage (MV) grid network for cost-effective grid extension, while balancing it with off-grid solutions in areas where grid expansion is not viable.
- The government should consider reversing the current planning approach by first running least-cost electrification models and then developing the national electrification budget based on realistic investment needs.
- Conduct a dedicated model to assess the investment required for 100% grid extension across Uganda and compare its fiscal implications against a balanced approach that leverages off-grid technologies.
- Incorporate evolving household and commercial demand using updated UBOS surveys and socio-economic projections.
- Integrate data on agricultural processing, tourism, and small-scale industries to prioritize electrification in areas with high economic potential.

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